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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
IDW	International Data Week
WS	Workshop
AHM	All hands meeting
API	Application programming interface
PID	Persistent identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings
MSCR	Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
GUPRI	Globally Unique, Persistent and Resolvable Identifier

Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the activities undertaken by the FAIR-IMPACT Task 4.4 - FAIR Mappings working towards the establishment of guidelines and methodology to create, document and share mappings and crosswalks between semantic artefacts. The objectives of this task were to establish a framework enabling the creation of FAIR mappings that includes a set of technical recommendations (guidelines) and a practical mapping framework supporting the mapping process (methodology). To create this framework, the task has been actively engaging with a wide range of communities in various contexts (for example, workshops organised by the task, participation in international workshops, RDA plenary meetings). Through these engagement activities, the task has collected responses through an open survey to understand the common practices around mappings and collected feedback from experts to create the FAIR Mapping recommendations and the Practical Mapping Framework. In the process of establishing the FAIR recommendations, we identified a key scalability problem that was not foreseen by the FAIR principles and that may require some adaptation of the principles. Finally, the strong engagement of communities in the RDA context led to the creation of the FAIR Mapping Working Group which represents a sustainability path for the project outputs. This work has been done in close collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and in particular the team developing the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry.

1. Introduction

The focus of this deliverable is to establish a framework to make mappings between semantic artefacts FAIR. The first question we aim to answer is “what do we mean by mappings?”. In the context of this work, we define mappings as: *“connections or relationships between different information elements by identifying similarities, correspondences, and alignment. Mappings include different types of connections, depending on the level of the elements that are being mapped”* (Martinkova et al., 2024)¹. In addition, we defined crosswalks as sets of mappings connecting two information artefacts (e.g. metadata schema, ontologies...). This definition of mapping is quite generic, as we uncovered the complexity of the mapping realm during the project. Mappings can be used to connect semantic artefacts together, to connect metadata schemas for metadata conversion, both supporting interoperability and findability. In addition, they can be used at the level of the dataset for data integration, of APIs for system integration and as we discuss more and more with communities, we discover new usage and types of mappings.

Mappings have been identified as key components for semantic interoperability in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (Corcho et al., 2021)². They enable the creation of a network of semantic artefacts and interconnect information systems together. The creation of mappings requires a huge amount of human effort. Since, as in most cases, existing mappings are not easy to find, come in different shapes and forms that are not interoperable and prevent their reuse, this requires unavoidable repeated work of re-implementing the same mappings. In short, mappings are not FAIR. This situation has been well described in the SEMAF report,³ (Broeder et al., 2021) which investigated mapping practices and solutions with 25 interviews and pointed out the need for mappings to be FAIR. One of the SEMAF recommendations was the need to share and publish mappings and crosswalks in a dedicated registry, such as the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)⁴ developed in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.⁵ In the context of the FAIRsFAIR project,⁶ the FAIR Semantics recommendations (Le Franc et al., 2022)⁷ emphasized the need for mappings and crosswalks to be serialised into a machine-readable format (P-Rec11) and documented, published and curated (P-Rec12). These two recommendations highlighted the necessity for FAIR Mappings as contributors for FAIR semantic artefacts. The main reason is that common practices embed the mappings directly within the semantic artefact making them difficult to access, change and reuse in other contexts.

¹ <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3882/>

² <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4651421>

⁴ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

⁵ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675295>

The aim of this work is to propose a framework comprising a set of guidelines and a methodology to create FAIR mappings.

To address this challenge, we focused our effort on three main objectives:

- Establish guidelines on how to make mappings FAIR in a scalable and reproducible way (see Section 3.3, *“FAIR Mapping recommendations”*).
- Engage with communities to co-create, test and adopt the model for FAIR mappings and to identify methodologies and practices around mappings (see section 2, *“Engaging with the communities”* and section 3.1, *“Survey: Collecting the ways of doing mappings”*).
- Establish a methodology to create, document and share mappings and crosswalks including a governance framework in collaboration with the relevant FAIR-IMPACT work on Semantic artefact disciplinary governance (Task 4.1) (see section 3.2, *“How to do mappings in practice? The practical mapping framework”*).

As mappings are widely used in research communities, we have been engaging extensively with communities to raise the awareness for the need of FAIR Mappings, collect inputs and information regarding the existing practices used to create, manage and maintain mappings, and establish community-driven recommendations on how to make mappings FAIR. For this purpose, we organised workshops, contributed extensively to community events to present our work, identify new use cases, and to iteratively refine our work through community co-creation.

This work led to several outputs: a survey on existing community mapping practices, a methodology, called *“the practical mapping framework”* capable of accommodating those practices, providing a structured mapping process with support points addressed during the different phases of the process and a set of guidelines on how to make these mappings FAIR, once they have been created, the FAIR Mapping recommendations.

In this report, we will first present our approach, and particularly our community engagement activities. We will then present a summary of the results of the task i.e. the mapping practice survey, the practical mapping framework and the recommendations. The practical mapping framework and the FAIR Mapping recommendations are described in more detail in other documents^{8,9}. To avoid overloading this report, we thus chose to provide an overview of the results with the reference to the documents and discuss some specific related issues. Finally, we will describe our approach to sustain this work and extend its reach beyond the project.

⁸ Practical mapping framework: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12521431>

⁹ FAIR Recommendations: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15105510>

2. Engaging with the communities

Mappings are a transversal problem that concern many communities attempting to integrate different systems together. Through the engagement with various stakeholders and communities, the team has gained a lot of insights on the problem of mappings.

2.1. Engaging with the communities: organising focused workshops on FAIR Mappings

During the project, practical workshops were organised to invite mapping practitioners from various communities to discuss mappings, with each workshop building upon the output of that previous. In total, three workshops were organised and a fourth is scheduled to run before the end of the project. The first workshop aimed at kickstarting the task and at collecting inputs from experts on the FAIR recommendations. The two follow-up workshops were focused on addressing one of the key topics identified during the first workshop i.e. how do we do mappings in practice?

In this section, we summarize the different workshops, their objectives and highlight some of the key information we collected.

The first workshop was titled “*Why Mappings Matter and how to make them FAIR?*”¹⁰ and was organised online on April 13th, 2023. This initial workshop was well attended with 120 registered participants and 95 attendees. The aim of this workshop was to introduce the need for FAIR Mappings, to investigate mappings in various communities and to collect information on the requirements for FAIR Mappings, as well as the types of mappings and existing tools and requirements to accomplish them. The presentations of the different speakers have been made available on Zenodo (Le Franc et al., 2023a)¹¹. These covered a diverse set of topics all relating to mappings: a view from the EOSC Interoperability task force, mappings in biodiversity, social sciences, potential tooling to capture mappings in a standard way (using SSSOM¹²) and ongoing work in FAIRCORE4EOSC on the Metadata Schemas Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)¹³. We provided a detailed report on the event with the collected information which has been published in Zenodo (Martínková et al., 2023)¹⁴. During this first workshop the issue of the lack of clear and documented processes for creating mappings was highlighted, and a discussion towards a first set of common working practices across communities was started (at least conceptually). To explore these topics, we organised two additional workshops to collect information on the practical aspects of the mapping process used in various communities.

¹⁰ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/why-mappings-matter-and-how-make-them-fair>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162873>

¹² <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

¹³ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8144450>

The first workshop on this topic titled “*Documenting mapping community practices*”¹⁵, which had 91 registrants, aimed at having an initial overview of the existing processes and to discuss with these communities, with a view to formalise a common set of phases which are used for mapping. The presentations were published on Zenodo (Le Franc et al., 2023b)¹⁶. Our objective was to create a common documented process that could potentially become a recipe in the FAIR Cookbook¹⁷. Based on the information gathered, we established a first version of the practical mapping framework described in the next section (section 3.2).

The second workshop on mapping practices, with 100 registrants, entitled “*Developing a mapping process framework*”¹⁸ aimed at introducing the initial version of the framework and to work with use-cases to evaluate the framework (Juty et al., 2024)¹⁹. Using the outcomes of these discussions, we updated the framework to a second version²⁰. The feedback from this workshop, which comprised five targeted breakout sessions trialling the initial framework, has been used to refine the framework (see section 3.2).

A final workshop covering both this topic and the FAIR Mapping recommendations will be held on May 7th 2025²¹. During this workshop, we aim to collect community feedback on the practical mapping framework and the FAIR Mappings recommendations, and to address more specifically the question of the governance of the mappings. For example, once a mapping set has been generated, who maintains it over the long time.

In addition to these workshops, we co-organised six workshops in collaboration with FAIRCORE4EOSC to extend our outreach to the international communities:

- A workshop in collaboration with the Monarch Initiative and the SSSOM community as a satellite event of the 16th annual International Conference on BioCuration,²² on April 23rd, 2023.
- A session at SciDataCon during the International Data Week, held in Salzburg in 2023 and entitled “Building a semantic interoperability framework: towards FAIR mappings and crosswalks (session ID 512)”²³.
- A RDA Bird of Feather (BoF) during the co-located RDA plenary 21, entitled “Let’s talk about FAIR mappings! Towards common practices for sharing mappings and crosswalks”²⁴.

¹⁵ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/documenting-mapping-community-practices>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245143>

¹⁷ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/home.html>

¹⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/developing-mapping-process-framework>

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11094911>

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12521431>

²¹ <https://www.fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/moving-towards-fair-mappings-technical-recommendations-common-practices>

²² <https://biocuration2023.github.io/>

²³ <https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2023-Salzburg/sessions/512/programme>

²⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/let%E2%80%99s-talk-about-fair-mappings-towards-common-practices-sharing-mappings-and-crosswalks>

Following up this event, we organised additional Bird of Feather sessions during RDA plenaries (P22²⁵, P23²⁶, P24²⁷).

We also contributed with a joint presentation to the FAIR IMPACT synchronisation workshops on Metadata, Semantics and Interoperability in 2024²⁸ and a National Roadshow event (Austria²⁹).

2.2. Contributing to community related events.

To increase community awareness, we have been invited to present the work of the task in eight events during the project. The list of events is presented here in Table 1. The events all cover issues related to metadata and semantic artefact mappings.

Event	Community	Date
RDA Vocabulary and Semantic Service Interest Group session RDA P21	RDA - ontology experts from multiple communities	24th October 2023
NFDI Terminology services	Multiple NFDI communities involved in terminology issues	9th April 2024
Semantics@Roche	Pharmaceutical companies working on mapping of semantic artefacts	28th May 2024
FAIR principles for Ontologies and Metadata in Knowledge Management workshop	Ontology experts	15th July 2024
OSCARS consolidation and terminology workshop	OSCARS communities involved in terminology issues	1st October 2024
RDA France - Réunion plénière	RDA - multiple French communities	11th October 2024
RDA Vocabulary and Semantic Service Interest session RDA P23	RDA - ontology experts from multiple communities	13th November 2024

²⁵ https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/yann-le-franc/plenary-participation/?application_id=180617

²⁶ https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/yann-le-franc/plenary-participation/?application_id=180617

²⁷ https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/plenary-participation/?application_id=174625

²⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/synchronisation-force-workshop-series-2024-edition>

²⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/events/national-roadshows/fair-impact-national-roadshow-austria>

RDA Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG	RDA - Material Science experts	14th November 2024
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Table 1. List of events T4.4 contributed to

Our participation in the FAIR principles for Ontologies and Metadata in Knowledge Management workshop³⁰ was valorised by a peer-reviewed workshop paper, co-located with a conference, published in CEUR conference proceedings (Martinkova et al., 2024)³¹. During this session, we presented both the practical mapping framework and the FAIR Recommendations.

2.3. Contributing to external initiatives

During the project, we also directly contributed to major initiatives to bring in our expertise and perspectives on mappings to these initiatives.

2.3.1. EOSC Semantic Interoperability Task Force

Following up the publication of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (Corcho et al., 2021)³², the EOSC Association created a Task Force dedicated to Semantic Interoperability with the aim to explore semantic interoperability solutions, establish knowledge exchange around semantic interoperability and provide recommendations. The inception of this Task Force occurred at the beginning of the FAIR-IMPACT, and we chose to make a direct contribution to this Task Group to tackle the mapping aspect of semantic interoperability and exchange with leading experts on the specific problem of mappings. In this work, we highlighted the importance of FAIR Mappings and proposed four specific recommendations on mappings related to the ongoing work in the task (Nyberg Åkerström et al., 2024)³³. The recommendations are as follows:

1. **Define and standardise representations** (building on existing work such as SSSOM) to cover the wide range of possible qualified relationships between semantic concepts (e.g. entity mappings, schema crosswalks) **that can support mediated data discovery and data integration in EOSC.**
2. **Ensure that mappings, crosswalks and other specifications** created by EOSC projects to enable mediation across different combinations of semantic artefacts and Metadata Frameworks **are documented and shared according to the FAIR principles**, e.g. by leveraging the recommendations developed in the context of the FAIR-IMPACT project.
3. **Develop and establish best practices** for implementing and sharing toolsets that enable semantic interoperability through mediation, such as entity mappings and

³⁰ <https://onto4fair.github.io/foam/>

³¹ <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3882/>

³² <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>

³³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843882>

schema crosswalks with metadata **that ensure consistency and reliability in their usage.**

4. **Develop and establish effective governance mechanisms** to oversee and manage the process of creating, maintaining, versioning and using mappings and crosswalks to guarantee their utility, enforce consistency and reduce redundancy **in EOSC.**

In addition to this final output, we also contributed to the presentation of the EOSC Semantic Interoperability Task Force work during the second Workshop on Ontologies for FAIR and FAIR Ontologies (David et al., 2023)³⁴, including a questionnaire inspired from the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP, Magagna et al., 2022)³⁵ to collect and analyse solutions developed for Semantic Interoperability into a Semantic Interoperability Profile (SIP, Magagna et al., 2023)³⁶. Finally, we presented a poster during the RDA Plenary 21 (Baumann et al., 2023)³⁷. This work should be used by the new EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force³⁸.

2.3.2. CDIF

In addition to the contribution to this EOSC Association Semantic Interoperability Task Force, we were invited to participate in two Dagstuhl workshops^{39,40} to investigate the problem of mappings in relation to data integration. This work confirmed that the concept of mappings does not only apply to semantic artefacts but also to data models. Mappings are inter-related and add an additional level of complexity with respect to data integration.

This work enabled us to provide our insights to the CDIF Working Group and directly contribute as a member of the CDIF Working Group. We raised awareness on the problems of mappings and how to make them FAIR and in the meantime, we also uncovered additional use-cases to be considered in the framework that should also be used in the context of the RDA FAIR Mapping WG⁴¹ (see section 4 - Sustaining the FAIR Mapping Framework).

3. Guidelines and methodology

3.1. Survey “Collecting the ways of doing mappings”

To understand the different practices in the communities, we created a survey to collect information from the different communities engaged with this work. The survey contains 26

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8102786>

³⁵ <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e94451>

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10521533>

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10012280>

³⁸ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/technical-and-semantic-interoperability-task-force/>

³⁹ <https://www.dagstuhl.de/en/seminars/seminar-calendar/seminar-details/23403>

⁴⁰ <https://www.dagstuhl.de/en/seminars/seminar-calendar/seminar-details/24423>

⁴¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/activity/>

questions focused on the creation, re(use), governance and documentation of the mappings (for the full questionnaire, see Annex 1). The survey has been published on the FAIR-IMPACT website and is maintained open until the end of the project.⁴² As of this report, we have collected a total of 18 responses which have been analysed. The results of the survey are presented below.

The first part of the survey aimed at capturing socio-demographic information about the respondents to better understand their profile i.e. location, profession and domain of expertise⁴³ (see Figure 2). We received answers from 10 different countries with a bias toward European respondents.

Figure 1. Socio-demographics of the respondents

Most of the respondents have a multidisciplinary background with a strong bias toward Natural science and Medical and Health Science. The received answers cover all the domains considered by the survey. Most of the respondents have a research position (64%) with activities around data such as data provider, service provider or data curator. We also received answers from service providers (mostly repository developers/managers) and a semantic engineer.

In the second part of the survey, we asked the respondents how they work with mappings and more precisely if they create mappings, reuse mappings or both. 62,5% of the respondents do both, 25% create mappings and only 12,5% reuse mappings. We then tried to understand how they contribute to the mapping process i.e. creating the mappings, curating and evaluating the mappings, producing metadata to describe the mappings, defining the publishing policies and publishing the mappings on the web. Figure 3 shows the distribution of the answers. Most of the respondents contribute to the creation and the curation phase of the mapping process. About a third of the respondents participate in all the

⁴² <https://fair-impact.eu/collecting-ways-doing-mappings-webform>

⁴³ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/B.+v4.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile#B.v4.00EOSCResourceProfile-ResourceScientificDomain>

stages and another third only focus on the creation, curation and documentation aspects of the process.

Figure 2. Contribution to the mapping process

We then investigated what types of entities (semantic artefact classes, instances and properties, metadata fields, entities in a database and enumeration/code list) are mapped and for what purpose (data standardisation, data enrichment, indexation, integration or other). The results are presented in Figure 4 below.

Figure 3. Types of entities mapped and purpose of the mapping

In most of the answers, mappings are not solely restricted to semantic artefacts but also involve several other types. The same applies for the purpose of the mappings.

In the next questions, we were interested in tooling and metadata. Spreadsheets emerged as the most widely used tool for mappings, with 11 out of 18 respondents indicating their reliance on them. Metadata practices varied among respondents, though several key metadata elements were commonly recorded (see Figure 5). The most frequently provided metadata element is the date of creation of a mapping (75%), followed by the creator's name (68%), the mapping method used (62%), and the source and target schema IDs (62%). Licensing information was included in 56% of mappings.

Figure 4. Metadata fields for documenting mappings

Concerning publishing mappings, roughly half of the respondents reported relying on institutional or national servers rather than standardized public repositories, indicating that publication methods are often determined by institutional or national contexts. Otherwise, mappings are published on GitHub, Zenodo and in some cases in preprints/publications.

Mappings are typically published in multiple formats with spreadsheets being the most common (used by 60% of respondents). RDF, XML, and JSON-LD formats are also frequently used, though at a significantly lower rate (see Figure 6).

Figure 5. Format and predicates

We then asked the respondent if they provide an explicit relation between the mapped entities or if they use an implicit relation i.e. a correspondence table with 2 columns. 59% of the respondents use explicit relations. The predicates (i.e. the relation linking the two mapped entities) most used are 'exact' matches and 'close' matches, each employed by 90% of the respondents, followed by 'related' matches, used by 70% of the respondents (see Figure 6). Some respondents also reported using predicates from SKOS and OWL standards such as skos:broadMatch, owl:equivalentClass, owl:sameAs, skos:closeMatch, skos:narrowMatch,

owl:equivalentProperty or other relations such as subsumption relationships, and concatenation.

Following these guided questions, we asked participants open-ended questions regarding their challenges when doing mapping, how they use and reuse mappings and about the governance of the mappings.

The respondents identified several challenges in their mapping activities related to defining and selecting terms, managing versioning and updates, and ensuring governance and sustainability. Encoding challenges are also reported, particularly in terms of handling complex mappings, and choosing appropriate formats. Publishing mappings posed additional challenges, as respondents struggled with issues such as format inconsistencies, duplication, the need for versioning, and the lack of standardized unique identifiers for mappings.

Regarding the usage of the mappings, most respondents indicated that mappings are primarily used for data integration and standardization, enabling interoperability across different terminologies and ontologies. Mappings are also employed in metadata services, supporting activities such as search, annotation, and metadata transformation. While some respondents are unsure of how their mappings are ultimately used, others reported more specialized applications, including software development and federated querying across multiple systems. Half of the respondents reported that their mappings are automatically consumed by tools or software, particularly in knowledge graphs, ontology integration tools, and metadata repositories. Some respondents indicated that mappings played a role in genomics and phenology applications, while others mentioned their use in FHIR and terminology API applications.

When asked about their reuse of mappings created by others, responses were mixed. While some respondents 'always' or 'often' reused mappings, others did so only 'occasionally'. The most common sources for external mappings are repositories and mapping catalogues, followed by community-driven platforms and metadata catalogues. Some respondents relied on publications and web searches, while a smaller number referenced specific platforms such as FAIRsharing.org.

Conflicts arising from multiple mappings is a challenge for many respondents, and the most common approach is manual conflict resolution. Some reported that they did not encounter conflicts or were unaware of them, possibly due to working in more controlled environments. A few respondents used specialized tools to detect and manage conflicts, while others addressed issues by clarifying the source and version of mappings or evaluating the quality of the original data sources.

Assessing the quality of reused mappings is another area of interest. While seven respondents reported that they actively evaluated the quality of mappings before reuse, six did not perform any formal evaluation. Among those who did, there is no single dominant approach; rather, they relied on a combination of trusted sources, peer review, collaboration with original creators, and expert judgment.

Governance of mappings varied significantly among respondents. Half of them reported dealing with different versions of their mappings, most commonly using GitHub or GitLab for version control. Others relied on version numbers, publication dates, or schema updates to manage different versions. However, for those who did not track versions, the main reason is that versioning was not considered necessary or had not yet been implemented in their workflows. When asked about formal governance processes within their organizations or groups, most respondents reported that they did not have documented governance procedures in place. Some organizations had governance documentation for specific projects, but for many, this remained a work in progress.

Finally, the curation and evaluation of mappings were explored. While eight respondents actively curated and evaluated mappings, seven did not engage in any formal curation. The most common approach to curation is expert review, often combined with syntactic validation using tools such as SSSOM. Some respondents updated mappings in response to changes in schema versions or metadata standards, while others used graphical interfaces or informal curation methods.

In summary, the survey highlighted a diverse range of practices in mapping creation and reuse, with varying levels of formalization in metadata practices, publishing workflows, and governance structures. While many respondents recognized the importance of mappings for data standardization and integration, challenges remained in encoding, versioning, and conflict resolution. The findings suggest a need for more standardized practices and shared governance frameworks to support mapping sustainability and interoperability.

These answers have been partially used to establish the practical mapping framework. The anonymized dataset and the analysis are available on Zenodo⁴⁴.

3.2. How to do mappings in practice? The practical mapping framework

Through a series of two workshops with numerous communities (Social Science and Humanities, Earth Science, Biodiversity, Environment, Marine, Life Science, Food and Agriculture, Research Software...), we have co-created a widely applicable and practical mapping framework. We identified several properties that such a framework should have from initial workshops. In particular, the framework should:

- be usable in a domain agnostic manner,
- reflect the different common conceptual phases of mappings,
- facilitate the capture of the mapping context,
- capture versions of mappings, and
- be findable, to avoid duplication of work.

Having identified the different ‘phases’ that constitute a mapping, as well as the properties that such a framework should possess, we built a framework, which consists of 5 phases: ‘pre-mapping’, ‘mapping’, ‘review’, ‘hosting’, and ‘maintenance’ (Figure 1).

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15105565>

Figure 6. Practical Mapping Framework process

The purpose of the framework is to guide researchers who wish to undertake a mapping to systematically address practical considerations and hence collect the appropriate context and use case underlying it, and thereby the key metadata that needs to be shared with the mapping itself, to make it useful and usable by other researchers.

The different phases of the framework reflect the common way in which mapping is accomplished across communities, and notably, each phase has a defined input and output. Each phase is outlined below:

The **pre-mapping phase** is the foundation of the process, where key decisions must be made that influence or define downstream tasks. For instance, this phase involves discussion with various stakeholders to define concretely the source and targets for mapping, the mechanisms or methodologies to be used, and for instance which licence will be applied to the resulting work. The requirements to enter this phase are simply a defined ‘use case’, with the output being a ‘protocol’, which in turn feeds the next phase: mapping. The protocol consists of all the decisions made in this pre-mapping phase, including the chosen mechanisms, methodologies, and other relevant factors.

The **mapping phase** is the practical implementation of the mapping itself, as defined in the protocol. This may practically be a manual effort, or through automated or semi-automated mechanisms. The output of this phase is an initial mapping file, in the format described by the protocol, that enters the ‘review’ phase.

The **review phase** assesses the applicability of the mapping exercise in the context of the use case. Depending on the collective decision of the reviewers, the mapping file can be accepted, whereupon the process moves to the hosting phase, or else the process will have to fall back to the protocol (for minor refinements), or else require further discussion, back in the pre-mapping phase, to get input from the wider stakeholders. Note that the selection of reviewers is not in scope of this phase and is a decision that must be made by stakeholders involved in the mapping.

In the **hosting phase**, the ‘accepted’ mapping file is uploaded to the agreed hosting resource, defined in the protocol most likely, along with metadata as appropriate for that resource. Resources that surface sufficient of the indexed metadata should have been selected in the pre-mapping phase, as well as the application of a suitable license. Once hosted, the mapping process moves into the ‘maintenance’ phase.

The **maintenance phase** targets the long-term availability, accuracy and ‘openness to feedback’ of the mapping itself, something that is defined in discussions in the pre-mapping phase. Fundamentally, this phase is initiated once the maintenance mechanisms, if any, agreed in the pre-mapping phase are activated, and the file remains in this phase in perpetuity.

Throughout these different phases, several aspects of the governance framework are defined. We are working in collaboration with T4.1, focusing on Semantic artefact disciplinary governance, to define a generic governance framework for mappings and crosswalks. A preliminary governance framework will be discussed during the fourth and final workshop organised by the task on May 7th 2025⁴⁵.

To guide users through this process, we created a narrative guide and a spreadsheet. The narrative guide defines each phase of the framework (pre-mapping, mapping, review, hosting, maintenance).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1		Premapping	Mapping	Review	Hosting	Maintenance	Expected values	Example	explanation/notes	usage notes for participants			
2	Date						YYYY-MM-DD	2024-04-30	date of completion				
3	Participant name*						First name, Last name	Roger Rabbit					
4	Institution* (optional)						text or URI	The University of Manchester					
5	Participant id *						ORCID or ROR		ROR where a 'group' acknowledgment is needed				
6	Participant role (optional)*						text	use case owner	use role from stakeholder terms in framework				
7	Document location						URI	https://zenodo.org/xyz	could be this document, or where it is uploaded				
8	Document version						URI		each version should be dated, and attributed				
9													
10	Use case description						text		Terse description of the use case being addressed.				
11													
12													
13													
14	definitions	We provide the following definitions to ease the understanding and scope/context of this framework. We by no means intend these to be interpreted as 'formal' and agreed outside of this body of work											
15	semantic artefact	Semantic artefact is an umbrella term coined for use during FAIRsFAIR, and includes ontologies, thesauri, controlled vocabularies, taxonomies, metadata schemas and standards. It is a pragmatic solution.											

Figure 7. Spreadsheet to guide the mapping process

For each phase, there is a description of the activities constituting the phase, a list of anticipated stakeholders that should be involved, an indication of the types of questions that need to be answered, as well as the formalisation of inputs and outputs for each phase, and hence what is needed to move between phases. The ‘spreadsheet’ provides a convenient means by which discussion and decisions can be recorded. It is not intended to be used as a format in of itself, but we anticipate it may provide a lightweight mechanism for simpler

⁴⁵<https://www.fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/moving-towards-fair-mappings-technical-recommendations-common-practices>

mappings. The spreadsheet is organised into sheets per phase, with a top sheet to record higher level metadata (date of mapping, version, participants per phase, etc). The materials (narrative guide & spreadsheet) are available on [Zenodo](#) (Juty et al., 2024)⁴⁶.

The practical mapping framework has been tested by different communities during the second workshop organised on this topic and has been adopted by the British Oceanographic Data Centre and is currently being tested by the Research Software community to revise CodeMeta mappings⁴⁷.

3.3. The FAIR Mapping recommendations

The main goal of this work is to identify the technical requirements that would be necessary to have mappings compliant with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016)⁴⁸ and establish a set of recommendations that would support their implementation.

First, we investigated existing initiatives and reports regarding mappings such as SEMAF (Broeder et al., 2021)⁴⁹, OAEI (Euzenat et al., 2011)⁵⁰, FAIR Semantics recommendations (Le Franc et al., 2022)⁵¹, SSSOM (Matentzoglou et al., 2022)⁵². This analysis of the landscape enabled us to assert several things.

The SEMAF report explicitly mentioned that mappings come in different forms and shapes and are being used in various contexts (e.g. metadata conversion, data conversion, semantic alignment between semantic artefacts API alignment, etc). In most of the cases, metadata mappings are either in the form of tables or logic in software code, sometimes they can be found as RDF. During this work, we identified the need for a clear classification to describe the different types of mappings and supporting smoother communication between experts.

Secondly, the investigation of the different models such as EDOAL⁵³, the Xref model used in the EBI OxO service⁵⁴ and SSSOM, revealed that SSSOM seems to be the more efficient model to support FAIR Mappings as it provides an extensive set of metadata fields to describe both the mapping set or crosswalk and the individual mappings. Mapping sets are associated with globally unique and persistent identifiers. SSSOM leverages a tabular format which is aligned with the current practices for doing mappings. Although SSSOM has been developed in the context of the Biomedical community, this model can be easily extended to cover any other domains. The main limitation of the model is the coverage in terms of mapping complexity. In contrast, the EDOAL model is more focused on complex ontology alignments extending the

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15000917>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/oeg-upm/codemeta-crosswalk-mapping-methodology>

⁴⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4651421>

⁵⁰ https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-22630-4_6

⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675295>

⁵² <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baac035>

⁵³ <https://moex.gitlabpages.inria.fr/alignapi/edoal.html>

⁵⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/spot/oxo/about>

Alignment API⁵⁵. This model has been developed to represent more complex mappings than subsumption and equivalence supporting data integration through pattern correspondence between ontologies.

To collect additional information regarding mappings and additional requirements for FAIR Mappings, we organised workshops involving experts from a wide range of communities (see section 1, engaging with communities, etc). Most of the requirements were in line with the requirements identified in SEMAF.

To align the recommendations to the FAIR principles, we chose to cluster the FAIR Principles into four main categories:

- Persistent identifiers
- Metadata
- Format and model
- Service and API

This clustering approach accommodates recommendations that can fulfill several individual FAIR principles.

At the time of writing, we have converged on 18 recommendations which includes a generic recommendation for each category and additional technical recommendations. In this report, we provide the list of recommendations, the FAIR Principles they address and the specific stakeholder (i.e. the mapping author and service provider) which will be impacted by the recommendation, and we discuss specific aspects of the recommendations. These recommendations and the rationale for these recommendations are described in more detail in a separate document⁵⁶ which will be regularly updated with the feedback collected from the communities. Based on the comments received from the community, we will publish a second version of the recommendations by the end of the project.

3.3.1. Model and format

ID	Recommendation	Stakeholder	FAIR principles covered
G-Rec 1	Use a model to represent mappings with explicit links between the mapped entities and metadata for the crosswalk and the individual mappings that can be serialised in various formats	Mapping author	R1, R1.2, R1.3, I1

⁵⁵ <https://moex.gitlabpages.inria.fr/alignapi/format.html>

⁵⁶ FAIR Mapping recommendations: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15105510>

T-Rec 1.1	Use the SSSOM model to structure and share your mappings	Mapping author	R1, R1.2, R1.3, I1
T-Rec 1.2	Provide the mappings with different serialisations including LD standards (RDF/XML, OWL/XML, JSON-LD)	Mapping author	I1
T-Rec 1.3	Make sure the metadata describing the crosswalks and the individual mappings are aligned with standards and FAIR vocabularies to structure the metadata (e.g. Dublin Core, DCAT...)	Mapping author	I1, I2

Table 2. Model and format: recommendations

Our main recommendation is to adopt SSSOM as much as possible, knowing that the coverage of SSSOM is limited to simple one-to-one mappings and a subset of more complex mappings. This recommendation applies to the format and model cluster. The rationale for this recommendation is that SSSOM leverages a simple tabular format, which is in line with the most used format in the mapping community and can be serialised as RDF. Furthermore, it provides an extensive and generic metadata schema for documenting Crosswalks and individual mappings. As SSSOM covers most of the classical use-cases for mappings, we also recommend using it as the main exchange format. Indeed, it provides a compact format that encapsulates the mappings and the associated metadata into a table that can be then converted into RDF, which would be the most favoured format to leverage mappings. The main reason for this relates to the nature of mappings which link information entities together. The best model for representing such links remains the W3C RDF model which proposes the triplet model which connects a subject with an object through a relation called predicate. However, the use of this model entails a strong technical requirement which is the use of URIs/IRIs as identifiers for each part of the triplet. This constraint can be easily addressed in the context of semantic artefacts such as ontologies, controlled vocabularies, thesaurus leveraging related standards such as SKOS or OWL. This will not be the case for instance for metadata schemata in XML or JSON, which are not associated with resolvable namespaces and even associated with a unique identifier.

3.3.2. Metadata

ID	Recommendation	Stakeholder	FAIR principles covered
G-Rec 2	Provide metadata to describe the crosswalks and individual mappings	Mapping author	F1, R1, I3

T-Rec 2.1	Use the minimum SSSOM metadata schema defined by the FAIR IMPACT project to document mappings and crosswalks	Mapping author	F1, R1, I3
T-Rec 2.2	Provide the mappings with different serialisations including LD standards (RDF/XML, OWL/XML, JSON-LD)	Mapping author	F3

Table 3. Metadata: recommendations

The second aspect of FAIR mapping recommendations concerns metadata which is an essential part of the FAIR principles. The metadata required for FAIR mappings should cover a broad range of aspects such as licence information, provenance, community specific metadata which will contribute to the different aspects of FAIR i.e. mostly Findability and Reusability. To identify the necessary metadata for representing FAIR Mapping, i.e. establishing a minimum metadata schema, we collected from the experts in the tasks, an exhaustive list of queries that users would like to use for retrieving and reusing existing mappings. We found out that all the metadata fields that we identified for answering all our queries are already part of the SSSOM metadata schema except for two metadata fields: “Source and target semantic artefact Name” and “Mapping context”. The first would be used to find mappings with respect to the semantic artefact they connect, and the second field has been requested by the communities during our various workshops and has been deemed essential for reusability. This element would be a perfect placeholder to connect the information collected by the Mapping Practical Framework described previously (see section 3.2). The details are published in a paper submitted to the FOAM workshop in 2024 (Martinkova et al., 2024)⁵⁷.

Based on this work, SSSOM is clearly the best match for enabling FAIR mapping, but it would still require some adjustments such as the attribution of PIDs for individual mappings which is currently discussed within the SSSOM community⁵⁸ and additions to the metadata schema.

3.3.3. Persistent Identifiers

ID	Recommendation	Stakeholder	FAIR principles covered
G-Rec 3	Crosswalks (collections of mappings), individual mappings, and their versions must be identified with a GUPRI	Mapping author	F1
T-Rec 3.1	Use web-based GUPRIs that enable the access to the SSSOM mapping metadata and	Mapping author	F1

⁵⁷ <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3882/>

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/mapping-commons/sssom/issues/359>

	data by content-negotiation (e.g. PURL, W3id...)		
T-Rec 3.2	Establish and publish a PID policy describing the approach for versioning and explicitly describe the preservation policies.	Mapping author	F1

Table 4. Persistent Identifiers: recommendations

The PID related issue is at the heart of the next cluster which aims at providing recommendations on the use of Globally Unique and Persistent Resolvable Identifiers (GUPRIs) required by the FAIR principles.

We emphasised, in one of the related recommendations, the need for providing such GUPRIs for each individual mapping. This would enable the possibility to reuse individual mappings from different crosswalks/mapping sets. Several existing approaches could be considered to provide GUPRIs for FAIR Mappings: DOIs, Handles, Persistent URLs (purl.org and w3id.org) or new approaches such as the W3C decentralised identifiers (DiD).⁵⁹

As the nature of the mappings is to connect things together, they fit well with the RDF framework which relies on the URI/IRI system for providing resolvable identifiers. Therefore, the natural GUPRI technology would be the web-based persistent identifiers systems. However, the current practices in Open Science lean more toward the use of DOIs as research object identifiers. As we have several technical options, it is difficult to provide a specific recommendation for FAIR Mapping besides the initial trend to use web-based systems relying on content negotiation. To investigate this further, we started to analyse the implications of implementing the GUPRIs as required by the FAIR principles. We established an initial generic GUPRI structure for a collection of mapping (see Figure 2 below), identifying all the necessary identifiers. We ended up with at least seven required identifiers for a collection with one mapping. We need an identifier for the mapping collection and one for the mapping collection metadata record. Similarly, we need an identifier for the individual mapping and one for the associated metadata record. Finally, the mapping connects three different entities i.e. the source, the target and the relation or predicate for the simplest case. Each of these elements must also have their GUPRI adding up 3 identifiers to the lot.

⁵⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-1.0/>

Figure 8. Abstract PID structure for crosswalks/mappings sets and individual mappings

This has a strong impact on the practical implementation of the FAIR principles as if we consider now the global use of mappings for discovery, this will entail most likely millions of individual mappings grouped together in most likely hundreds of thousands of mapping collections. The number of required identifiers becomes therefore huge, and the technical challenge will lie in the need for fast resolution of each identifier to address even simple queries.

To support this claim, we considered the CodeMeta Metadata Crosswalks.⁶⁰ This initiative created mappings between the CodeMeta schema which provide metadata for Software (currently in version 3, REF) and various other metadata schemata, including generic metadata schema such as DCAT, Datacite, Dublin Core or Figshare and more specific software package metadata (PyPi, Debian Package, NodeJS, etc). At the time of writing, 39 crosswalks could be retrieved from the GitHub repository. To estimate the total number of individual mappings, we counted the number of correspondences in each of the provided correspondence tables. For correspondence where several terms could apply, we counted each of them as individual mappings. In total, we estimated 762 individual mappings. If we now extend that to the initially defined GUPRI structure, considering that we only use 10 different predicates and that the CodeMeta schema contains 74 metadata fields, we will need 2448 different GUPRIs. This example highlights the unanticipated combinatorial problem we are facing when implementing the FAIR principles at a global scale. However, it does not reflect the full picture as we did not consider the problem of versioning mapping

⁶⁰ <https://github.com/codemeta/codemeta/tree/master>

sets/crosswalks and individual mappings which should in theory also be associated with their own GUPRIs.

Another issue related to the GUPRI is the lack of unique identifiers for information entities such as metadata schema, data models or even APIs which are often not publicly available. This impedes the effort as mappings relate unambiguously identified elements of these schema. A solution to this problem is provided by the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry, developed in the FAIRCORE4ESOC project, which allows users to upload and publish metadata schemas with a GUPRI that will uniquely identify the schema and its elements to support the creation of mappings.

3.3.4. Services and API

ID	Recommendation	Stakeholder	FAIR principles covered
G-Rec 4	Publish your collection of mappings or crosswalks and the associated metadata into a specialized repository such as MSCR that provides access for humans and machines.	Mapping author	F4, A, R
T-Rec 4.1	Mapping repositories must support GUPRIs (enable to use external ones or assign new ones)	Service provider	F1
T-Rec 4.2	Mapping repositories must extract and publish the metadata records for the crosswalk and each of the individual mappings.	Service provider	A1.1
T-Rec 4.3	Metadata records describing collections of mappings, individual mappings, as well as their versions must be identified with a GUPRI	Service provider	F1
T-Rec 4.4	Mapping repositories may allow procedure of authorisation and authentication	Service provider	A1.2
T-Rec 4.5	Mapping repositories should allow accessibility to mapping metadata even when the mapping is no longer available	Service provider	A2
T-Rec 4.6	Mapping repositories must provide search functionality for mappings and collections of mappings.	Service provider	F4

T-Rec 4.7	Mapping repositories must use open standards and machine-readable descriptions to publish API description (e.g. OpenAPI, smartAPI)	Service provider	A1.1
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Table 5. Services and API: recommendations

The final part of the recommendation focuses on the services and APIs to access and use mappings, relating to the general recommendation to publish the mappings into a dedicated service, a mapping registry. These recommendations provide additional requirements to mapping services such as the Metadata and Schema Crosswalk Registry developed in the context of FAIRCORE4EOSC.

4. Sustaining the FAIR Mapping Framework

As explicitly mentioned in the SEMAF report and confirmed through our various workshops, mappings are a global and complex topic impacting all communities working with digital objects in the context of Open Science but also beyond. This has been reinforced by the attendance and strong engagement of the communities during the dedicated session we organised during the International Data Week and the co-located RDA Plenary.

One of the key outcomes from the RDA Bird of a Feather session organised during the IDW 2023- RDA P21 was the need for a dedicated RDA Working Group to support further and broader discussions and the establishment of more global recommendations on mappings and practical information related to mappings. This represents a unique opportunity to extend the outreach of our work and to sustain this work after the life of the project.

To leverage this opportunity, we invested a considerable amount of effort in maintaining the momentum created during the RDA Plenary 21 by organising regular Bird of Feather meetings in the subsequent RDA plenaries (RDA P22⁶¹ and RDA P23⁶²).

These two events have been used to present the FAIR Mapping recommendations and collect initial feedback and to discuss the creation of a dedicated Working Group on FAIR mappings which enable international communities to contribute to the overall work.

This FAIR Mapping Working Group has been created, in close collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and aims at producing a classification of mappings, common guidelines to make different types of mappings FAIR, including a set of representations for each of the types.

The FAIR Mapping WG is unique in the context of RDA as it connects several IG and WG in RDA which are concerned with mappings such as the Metadata IG, the Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Interoperability Framework WG, the Harmonised terminologies and schema for FAIR

⁶¹ https://www.rd-alliance.org/members/yann-le-franc/plenary-participation/?application_id=180617

⁶² https://www.rd-alliance.org/session_entry/birds-of-a-feather-session-application-01-07-2024/

data in Material Sciences, the Brokering Framework WG; FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG, i-ADOPT WG, etc.

The FAIR Mapping WG should deliver an extensive framework for FAIR Mappings that includes the outputs of the projects (i.e. the FAIR mapping recommendations and the Practical Mapping Framework) which should become, after revision by the communities, RDA recommendations with a global extent. In addition to these outputs, the Working Group will create a collection of harmonised use-cases description, a classification of mappings and a set of associated data models and the associated metadata. These different outputs will be connected into a Knowledge Base, providing a solution for the current most important gap, highlighted by the communities, training resources and guidelines.

The FAIR Mapping WG⁶³ was endorsed in February 2025 and already started working with bi-weekly meetings. This work is done in collaboration with the SSSOM community, and the content of the Working Group is hosted in the Mapping Commons repository,⁶⁴ managed by the SSSOM community.

5. Conclusions

During the project, we realised together with the engaged communities that mappings are much more complex than just aligning semantic artefacts: mappings are part of a more global framework enabling the interconnection of information systems to support various needs such as retrieval across information systems or disciplinary and cross disciplinary data integration. Mappings between semantic artefacts play an important role in the semantic interoperability aspect and enable the “knitting” of heterogeneous and distributed systems which is crucial for supporting global findability. However, it only represents a fraction of the problem and should be extended to the other types of mappings to guarantee the implementation of the FAIR principles at a global scale and fostering data reuse. Mappings are a key component of interoperability solutions and therefore, are linked with the work done in the task T6.1 - Semantic and Technical core interoperability across domains, which aims at providing guidelines for enabling cross domain interoperability. The FAIR Mapping recommendations will be one of the components supporting both interoperability and the alignment with the FAIR principles.

The work initiated by the FAIR-IMPACT had a strong impact on the community, as demonstrated by the active engagement of the various communities in the workshops that were organised in the specific context of the project but more importantly during the various sessions we organised in the more global context of the Research Data Alliance.

This strong engagement led to the creation of the FAIR Mapping WG which was endorsed by RDA in February 2025 and already counts 60 members. This Working Group will serve as a unique platform for collecting inputs on the project outputs from the international community and to publish these results beyond the usual European scope, as RDA

⁶³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/activity/>

⁶⁴ <https://github.com/mapping-commons/rda-fair-mappings>

recommendations, ensuring the sustainability of this work. The work, done in the context of RDA, is born from a strong collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and in particular the team involved in the development of the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry.

The continuous work of the task on establishing recommendations to make mappings FAIR, uncovered several major issues related to the current practices regarding metadata and mappings. In particular, one of these issues is related to the fact that essential information entities such as metadata schema, machine readable API descriptions, data models, crucial for implementing the FAIR principles and more precisely the machine actionability side of the FAIR principles, are not themselves FAIR. This has a major impact on our capabilities to perform mappings between these entities. The FAIRCORE4EOSC project is providing an initial solution with the publication of metadata schema in the MSCR and their association with a GUPRI which allows to uniquely and unambiguously identify the different elements to be mapped.

The second main issue is a scalability issue when implementing FAIR principles at a low level of granularity (for mappings but also for other digital objects). The principles emphasise the necessity to provide GUPRIs for the data and the metadata record and to link the data and the metadata by adding the GUPRI of the data inside the metadata record. In the context of mappings, this implies to generate and resolve a very large number of GUPRIs when using them (see section 3.3 - FAIR Mapping recommendations for more details). As mappings act as the glue between a very heterogeneous data and metadata landscape, the number of mappings is bound to explode exponentially leading to a combinatorial expansion of the necessary GUPRIs. Such a scalability issue was not considered at the time of the FAIR principles creation as the principles were designed to be high level. Now that we are seriously considering their implementation in the context of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) but also in other international initiatives, this issue becomes more apparent and would require us to reconsider possibly the initial FAIR principles related to the GUPRIs. This prevented us from making a strong recommendation for the type of GUPRIs to use for mappings and will require us to compare the existing solutions at scale and investigate possible solutions to simplify the current GUPRI model. This has been highlighted both in this document but also in the FAIR Mapping recommendations as this problem should be addressed together with the international communities. This work will be pursued, after the end of the project, in the context of the RDA FAIR Mapping WG. The FAIR Mapping recommendations and the practical mapping framework will contribute to the further refinement of the EOSC Interoperability Framework that will support the creation of the EOSC Federation, to build a web of FAIR data and services.

References

- European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Corcho, O., Eriksson, M., Kurowski, K. et al., EOSC interoperability framework – Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/620649>
- Broeder, D., Budroni, P., Degl'Innocenti, E., Le Franc, Y., Hugo, W., Jeffery, K., Weiland, C., Wittenburg, P., & Zwolf, C. M. (2021). SEMAF: A Proposal for a Flexible Semantic Mapping Framework (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4651421>
- Yann Le Franc, Luiz Bonino, Hanna Koivula, Jessica Parland-von Essen, & Robert Pergl. (2022). D2.8 FAIR Semantics Recommendations Third Iteration (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675295>
- Yann Le Franc, Henriette Harmse, Luca De Santis, Keith Jeffery, Nicolas Matentzoglou, & Claus Weiland. (2023a). Why Mappings Matter and how to make them FAIR?. Why Mappings Matter and how to make them FAIR? Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8162873>
- Jana Martínková, & Yann Le Franc. (2023). FAIR-Impact's workshop: Why semantic mappings matter and how to make them FAIR? (Version 1). Why Mappings Matter and how to make them FAIR?. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8144450>
- Le Franc, Y., Goble, C., Leeflang, S., Kokkinaki, A., Bernal, I., McLaughlin, J., Jupp, S., Monteil, A., & Reijnhoudt, L. (2023b). Documenting mapping community practices. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10245143>
- Juty, N., Le Franc, Y., Goble, C., & Martínková, J. (2024). FAIR-IMPACT Task 4.4 Workshop: Developing a Mapping Process Framework (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12521432>
- Nyberg Åkerström, W., Baumann, K., Corcho, O., David, R., Le Franc, Y., Madon, B., Magagna, B., Micsik, A., Molinaro, M., Ojsteršek, M., Peroni, S., Scharnhorst, A., Vogt, L., & Widmann, H. (2024). Developing and implementing the semantic interoperability recommendations of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (27 March 2024). EOSC Association AISBL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10843882>
- David, R., Baumann, K., Le Franc, Y., Magagna, B., Vogt, L., Widmann, H., Jouneau, T., Koivula, H., Madon, B., Åkerström, W. N., Ojsteršek, M., Scharnhorst, A., Schubert, C., Shi, Z., Tanca, L., & Vancauwenbergh, S. (2023, Juillet 7). Converging on a Semantic Interoperability Framework for the European Data Space for Science, Research and Innovation (EOSC). 2nd Workshop on Ontologies for FAIR and FAIR Ontologies (Onto4FAIR) (Onto4FAIR), Sherbrooke, Québec (Canada). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8102786>
- Magagna, B., Baumann, K., David, R., Jouneau, T., Le Franc, Y., Koivula, H., Madon, B., Nyberg Åkerström, W., Ojsteršek, M., Scharnhorst, A., Schubert, C., Shi, Z., Tanca, L., Vancauwenbergh, S., Vogt, L., & Widmann, H. (2024). Proposal for the EOSC Semantic Interoperability Questionnaire. 2nd Workshop on Ontologies for FAIR and FAIR Ontologies (Onto4FAIR), Sherbrooke, Québec (Canada). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10521533>
- Magagna B, Schultes EA, Suchánek M, Kuhn T (2022) FIPs and Practice. Research Ideas and Outcomes 8: e94451. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.8.e94451>
- Baumann, K., David, R., Le Franc, Y., Vogt, L., Widmann, H., Juneau, T., Koivula, H., Madon, B., Nyberg Åkerström, W., Ojsteršek, M., Scharnhorst, A., Schubert, C., Shi, Z., TANCA, L., & Vancauwenbergh, S. (2023). Consulting with Global Data Communities to Converge on Semantic Interoperability Solutions for the European Data Space for Science, Research and Innovation (EOSC). Research Data Alliance's 21st Plenary (RDA P21), part of International Data Week (IDW 2023). (RDA P21, part of IDW 2023), Salzburg, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10012280>

Jana Martínková, Nick Juty, Alejandra Gonzalez Beltran, Carole Goble, Yann Le Franc, “Moving towards FAIR mappings and crosswalks”, Proceedings of the Joint Ontology Workshops (JOWO) - Episode X: The Tukker Zomer of Ontology, and satellite events co-located with the 14th International Conference on Formal Ontology in Information Systems (FOIS 2024), Enschede, The Netherlands, July 15-19, 2024. Vol 3882, <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3882/>

Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Euzenat, J., Meilicke, C., Stuckenschmidt, H., Shvaiko, P., Trojahn, C. (2011). Ontology Alignment Evaluation Initiative: Six Years of Experience. In: Spaccapietra, S. (eds) *Journal on Data Semantics XV. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 6720. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-22630-4_6

Nicolas Matentzoglou, James P Balhoff, Susan M Bello, Chris Bizon, Matthew Brush, Tiffany J Callahan, Christopher G Chute, William D Duncan, Chris T Evelo, Davera Gabriel, John Graybeal, Alasdair Gray, Benjamin M Gyori, Melissa Haendel, Henriette Harmse, Nomi L Harris, Ian Harrow, Harshad B Hegde, Amelia L Hoyt, Charles T Hoyt, Dazhi Jiao, Ernesto Jiménez-Ruiz, Simon Jupp, Hyeongsik Kim, Sebastian Koehler, Thomas Liener, Qinqin Long, James Malone, James A McLaughlin, Julie A McMurry, Sierra Moxon, Monica C Munoz-Torres, David Osumi-Sutherland, James A Overton, Bjoern Peters, Tim Putman, Núria Queralt-Rosinach, Kent Shefchek, Harold Solbrig, Anne Thessen, Tania Tudorache, Nicole Vasilevsky, Alex H Wagner, Christopher J Mungall, A Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM), *Database*, Volume 2022, 2022, baac035, <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baac035>

Annex 1: Mapping survey - Questionnaire

Title: How do you do mappings in practice?

Welcome and thank you for taking the time to participate in our survey for collecting the ways of doing mapping. Your valuable insights are crucial to helping us understand how the mappings are being done now.

By mappings (and crosswalks) we mean a process of establishing connections or relationships between different elements involving identifying similarities, correspondences and alignments between them. With diverse approaches to mapping, we aim to collect information on creation, documentation, encoding, publishing, and reuse. This survey targets individuals involved in producing, consuming, storing, or sharing mappings, aiming to identify common steps, practices, and tools in the mapping process. Your input is crucial to our understanding and improvement.

This survey takes around 25 minutes.

The data will be analysed by members of FAIR-IMPACT T4.4. In the final study the interviews will be listed by the names of the institutions. In our study we will use the information you have provided during the survey. However, we will not attribute any statements to a specific organisation, unless you have explicitly authorised us.

The original survey data will be stored in FAIR-IMPACT website and in the FAIR-IMPACT internal storage system and will only be accessed by the project partners. Your personal data (name and email address) are only collected to contact you for further inquiries if necessary. If you would like at any point to have your data deleted, you can send your request to the contact email address below. Personal data will only be kept for the duration of the project and will be deleted afterwards.

This research is being done by the FAIR-IMPACT project, Work Package 4, Task 4.4 “Semantic artefact mappings and crosswalks”, led by Yann Le Franc (e-Science Data Factory) and including task members from DANS, INRAE, INRIA, UPM, DataCite, STFC, and UNIMAN.

FAIR-IMPACT is a European project funded by the Horizon Europe program (grant number GA 101057344) with the aim of expanding FAIR solutions across Europe and supporting the establishment of a FAIR European Open Science Cloud. In our task that focuses on mappings and crosswalks, we believe in the importance of collaborating and involving the wider community to not only gather valuable insights and feedback on our work but also for identification of practices and methodologies around mapping.

By selecting the “I consent” button, you consent to the collection, processing, and storage of your personal data as outlined in our privacy policy. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you may choose to exit the survey at any point without consequence. If you have any concerns or questions about how your data will be handled, please refer to our [full privacy policy](#).

I consent

Can we name your institution in the final study? *[Y/N option - only one option possible]*

If you have any further questions, comments, or concerns, please contact Jana Martínková (jmartinkova@esciencefactory.com).

1. You are working
 - a. At an institution: *[mandatory, text field]*
 - b. country *[mandatory, text field]*
 - c. as a (e.g.: data provider, service or software provider, researcher ...) *[mandatory, text field]*

2. What is your domain/field? *[multichoice option, controlled list: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/B.+v4.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile#B.v4.00EOSCResourceProfile-ResourceScientificDomain> + Other, please specify]*

3. How do you work with mappings and crosswalks? [Options: I create mappings; I reuse mappings from others; I create mappings and reuse mappings from others]

I create mappings -> question 4 (and everything below, except 17, 18, 19, 20)

I reuse mappings from others -> only questions 17, 18, 19, 20

I create mappings and reuse mappings from others -> everything

Creating mappings

4. In which part(s) of the mapping creation process are you involved? *[multichoice option, controlled list: Creation of mappings; Curation and Evaluation of mappings; Provide metadata about mappings; Defining the publishing policies (licence, storage, access,...); Publish mappings on the web + All of them; Other, please specify]*
5. What kind of entities do you map together? *[multiple choice option, controlled list: Classes; Individuals or Properties in Semantic artefact (ontology, vocabulary,..); Entities in database; Enumeration/Codelist values; Metadata fields + Other, please specify]*
6. Why do you produce mappings/crosswalks? *[multichoice option, controlled list: data standardisation, data enrichment, indexation, integration + Other, please specify]*
7. Which tools / applications / software do you use to create and/or work with mappings?(e.g.: spreadsheet, ..) *[text field]*
8. What metadata do you provide about your mappings/crosswalks? *[provide our list - Author; Creator; Reviewer; Accuracy score; Date of creation of this version; Version; Licence; Context; Justification; Clarification of the rationale of this mapping; Source and target SAs' IDs; Source and target SAs' name; Version of the SAs; Mapping method; Software used to create the mapping (if any); Specific types of SA that are mapped; Source term and target term label; Source term and target term ID; Mapping predicate; - and respondent can checked and add*

another they are using + other, please specify; all of them; none; select all (to check all elements and uncheck what is not true)]

9. How do you publish/share the mappings/crosswalks and associated metadata? (Please provide the name of the tools you use) *[multiple choice, list: GitHub, Dedicated web page, Zenodo, Publications - preprint, Google Drive, OXO, + Other, please specify]*
10. In which format do you encode, represent and store your mappings? *[multichoice option, controlled list: Spreadsheets, RDF, JSON-LD, OWL, XML, XSD, XSLT + Other, please specify]*
11. How do you define the relationships between the terms you are mapping *[two options: implicitly in a correspondence table (two columns); explicitly with mapping predicates]*
 - a. If explicitly, what kind of mapping predicates do you use to encode your mapping? *[multiplechoice options, list: related, close match, exact match + Other, please specify]*
 - b. Which standards do you use for these mapping predicates? (e.g.: skos:match, owl:sameAs, owl:equivalentClass, [sio](#)) *[optional, text field]*
12. What difficulties do you encounter when creating the mappings/crosswalks? *[optional, text field]*

(Re)use of mappings

13. How are the mappings you created used? *[text field]*
14. Are your mappings automatically consumed by a tool/software? *[Y/N]* *[by consumed we mean used as an input by software tool]*
 - a. If yes, in which concrete application are your mappings (automatically) consumed? *[mandatory, text field]*
15. Do you (re)use mappings done by others? *[always / often / sometimes/ rarely / never]*

Always, often, sometimes means they reuse mappings (info for questions: 18, 19, 20)

16. If you reuse mappings done by others, where do you get these from? How do you find them? *[text field]*
17. If you reuse mappings done by others, how do you deal with conflicts coming from multiple miscellaneous mappings?(e.g.: Mapping 1 says that C1 and C2 are exactMatch and Mapping 2 says C1 and C2 are not, the evolution of mapping resources) *[text field]*
18. If you reuse mappings done by others, do you evaluate the quality of the mappings you want to reuse? *[Y/N]*
 - a. If yes, how do you do that? (e.g.: somebody recommended, publication) *[text field]*

Governance

19. Do you deal with different versions of your mappings? *[Y/N]*
 - a. If yes, how? (e.g.: what tool / software / application, versioning numbers, ..) *[text field]*

- b. If not, why not? (explain the reason(s) e.g.: we have only the first version of the mapping, we have not come up with a sufficient solution, ..) *[text field]*
20. Do you have a documented governance process for your organisation/group? *[text field]*
21. Do you curate/evaluate mappings? *[Y/N]*
- a. If yes, how do you curate and evaluate them? *[text field]*

Examples

22. Please provide us with some concrete examples of your mapping(s) along with a brief description. *[text field/dropbox]*

Documentation

23. Please attach documentation on mappings that can be shared with us for the purposes of the FAIR-IMPACT project. If you do not have documentation, please insert a brief description of how you create the mapping. *[text field/dropbox]* (e.g.: practical method of creation, syntax, ..)
24. If you have (shareable) documentation about mappings, where do you store and manage it? *[text field]* (e.g.: web, github, ..)